

THE SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE INTRODUCTION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE QUALITATIVE ORGANIZATION OF THE MUSICAL EDUCATION PROCESS

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific theoretical basis of introducing modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process, which are effective in the quality organization of music education in the educational process.

Key words: Music education, pedagogical technology, practice, methodology, individual and group work.

Introduction.

Comprehensive updates and positive changes are being implemented in the education system as well as in all areas in our country. The Law "On Education" "National Personnel Training Program" serves as a legal and organizational pedagogical basis for this.

Along with updating and improving the content of education and increasing the quality indicators, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers-trainers, to keep them in step with the development of science and science, especially those who can effectively use information technologies and interactive methods, which are widely used in all fields. One of the important tasks of today is training (re-training) to the level of being able to freely communicate with the computer and to be able to apply it in one's work to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson.

Modernization of the organization of the educational process and the implementation of its innovative forms and methods in order to achieve the quality and efficiency indicators envisaged at the crucial stage of the implementation of the national personnel training program cannot be delayed today. is an urgent issue. Therefore, the question of what are the object, subject, goals and tasks of advanced pedagogical technologies and what results will their application in the educational process give and how will it affect the improvement of educational content? It is not for nothing that it is being used. The incredibly fast and intense development process of science, technology and information transmission and exchange technologies, in turn, requires the enrichment of traditional methods with new modern and interactive methods in the field of education. So, in what aspects are interactive, modeled methods gaining advantage? What are its types, structural structure, forms and means of organizing educational processes, how does it differ from previously existing teaching (Education) methods, what are its results, and what is its monitoring and evaluation system? Each student-coach and pedagogue should be prepared for the questions that will be asked, and it is necessary to understand that it is the most important social order placed before them and to answer these questions.

Curriculums, model science programs, which are the main normative and programming documents for the implementation of the tasks defined in the "Law on Education" and the "National Personnel Training Program" for the modernization of education, new generation textbooks, educational methodical manuals reflecting the requirements for the content and level of education State educational standards based on the latest achievements of science and education no matter how much the educational process and the material of its organization are improved no matter how much the technical support is strengthened or modernized, the final result will ultimately depend on the professional knowledge, skills, creativity, initiative, pedagogic skills and It depends on the intellectual potential, the ability to interest students in the acquisition of knowledge in science, and the ability to realize the most necessary aspirations.

It should be noted that ensuring the quality and efficiency of education is the correct, meaningful and interesting organization of the educational process aimed at mastering the educational content of the pupil or student, in this process It is an important role to turn students into active individuals who are not just listeners in class, but active participants in training, who complete independent tasks, independent and creative thinkers, who can express their opinions freely, and who can defend their opinions. plays

It can be seen that such an organization of the educational process, first of all, requires consideration in the process of professional training of future teachers in family schools. Therefore, the professors-teachers working in family education should conduct the classes in the subject they are teaching in a technological way and prepare their students for this activity.

The study, observation and analysis of practical experiences in the application of pedagogical technologies to education show that the organization of training on the basis of interactive methods is becoming widespread in almost all stages of education. In our opinion, this should not lead to the conclusion that one or another type of pedagogical technology should be used in every lesson. When the advanced pedagogical technology is effective, it is interesting for students, it can direct them to active, independent and creative thinking and observation.

For this purpose, the teacher should choose the pedagogical technology taking into account the lesson topic, structure, students' interest, and if there are music lessons, they should use them taking into account the theoretical, practical, performance possibilities.

The main goals and objectives of the use of pedagogical technologies include the following: Organization, working in cooperation (teacher-student interaction), group and individual work, each lesson ensuring student activity, improving, analyzing, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, controlling, evaluating, etc.

In the process of teaching subjects, it is appropriate for each teacher to work according to the following preparation system for using pedagogical technologies:

- Defining the topic;
- Setting the goal correctly;
- Determining key words that should be mastered on the topic;
- Tasks 1,2,3,4.... determine;
- Creation of technological process scenario;
- 1. Individual work;
- 2. Working as a group (small group) and team;

3. Question-answer, discussion, cluster, brainstorming, etc. with the whole team.

- Regulations;
- Assessment;
- Conclusion;

Ready-made technologies that have been tested and have had positive (high) results are applied to the educational process. Currently, attention is being paid to the design of educational activities and the use of technologies specific to certain subjects. A similar situation can be seen in the experience of technologyization of music lessons. As an example of this, technologies such as "Concert lessons", "Quiz lessons", "Fun and clever lessons", "Musical journey", "I am a conductor" used by advanced pedagogues can be shown. What is meant by training design and what is it based on? Below are the stages of organizing the training process based on design:

- Collecting materials related to the subject of the lesson (Teacher's preparation on the subject);
- Determining the purpose and tasks of studying the subject;
- Choosing the type, form, methods and tools of the lesson;
- Taking into account the amount of time spent in the process of mastering the concept, knowledge, skills, and abilities provided for in the project (for example, planning the amount of time allocated to each activity in music lessons);
- Exercises, examples that form the basis of the results achieved at each stage (assignment, practical demonstration);
- Organizational structure and conclusion of the training, conclusions;

Regardless of the part of the lesson, its type (lecture, practical, seminar, and singing, listening to music, music literacy in music lessons), the students' psychological and physiological characteristics, levels of preparation (voice range), singing opportunities, age characteristics) should be taken into account. In this process, the main focus is on increasing the activity of students, teaching them to think independently, to think creatively, to develop executive skills, to work according to their needs and interests, to use their internal capabilities and talents, should be focused on developing the skills of self-control and independent learning.

Here we will focus on the remarkable features of the application of advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational environment:

- When learning any subject, students are not only taught, they are taught to study independently;
- The knowledge and concepts given to the students are not given ready-made, but the students are taught to collect and study the information and information related to the topic independently using the sources;
- Skills for working with curriculum, textbooks, manuals, lecture texts are formed;
- The student is trained to be able to express, defend and prove his opinion;

Currently, in all the educational system of our republic, especially in the system of higher pedagogical education, great importance is attached to raising the quality and efficiency of teacher training, and various pedagogical researches are being conducted in this regard. Most of these researches are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of education by introducing advanced pedagogical technologies in order to achieve the goal of education and its high results, and technologyization of education is one of the most important tasks. A teacher's

high pedagogical skills and level of knowledge are undoubtedly one of the important factors of education. An experienced teacher with high pedagogical skills does not simply explain the lesson. If we explain this on the example of music lessons, the teacher's speech skills, playing a musical instrument, singing, using various visual and technical tools play a big role in making the lesson interesting and meaningful. .

In music lessons, most of the students sing in imitation of the teacher, follow him, follow his example, the personal "example" of the teacher is important. Because practical performance takes the leading place in the lesson, no goal can be achieved with a dry narrative style. Carefully organized scientific and pedagogical training is one of the main factors that ensure the effectiveness of education. The teachers actively participating in this process regularly improve their pedagogical skills and serve as an example to others in ensuring the effectiveness of education and training, in bringing up a competent generation responsible for the future. Therefore, it is possible to achieve good results by constantly improving and encouraging the innovative activities and experiences of advanced pedagogues who conduct "Music culture" lessons at every level of education, including general education schools.

In connection with the organization of innovative activity on a scientific basis, the most important thing in the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational process is to take into account the readiness and interest of students for this activity and to choose the necessary technology. whether it is a school, a college or a higher educational institution, the main goal of an educational institution is to impart knowledge to a pupil or student. In addition to imparting knowledge, the teacher looks for the most convenient and effective ways of imparting knowledge and organizes the educational process in an interesting and meaningful way. Such activity itself can be called educational technology. Educational technology (from the Greek "tekhne" - skill, art, "logos" - means understanding, teaching) or pedagogical technology, introducing various ways and methods of pedagogical education into one's activity at the same time, it is necessary to make sure that this process will give results.

Important situations and circumstances in determining the process of pedagogical training for pedagogical technology: preliminary determination of the tasks that the pupil or student will face in the process of learning, the content of education at each stage of education (curriculum, program, essence of the subject, determining the availability of educational and methodological resources, determining knowledge and concepts, their degree of complexity and degree of compatibility with the student's knowledge and skills, education and training forms and tools (additional resources, question-and-answer, discussion, test preparation of questions, demonstrations, hearing using technical means, listening resources); Pedagogical technologies, such as planning the tasks assigned to the student in class and outside of class for the objective assessment of the student's acquired knowledge and skills in accordance with the criteria for evaluating the quality of the educational result and mastery level.

It is necessary to pay attention to the following in order to prepare future teachers for pedagogical activity in higher educational institutions of pedagogy:

1. To study the experiences of new and effective work secrets of teachers operating on the basis of a technological approach;
2. To increase the activity of pedagogues in the technological approach and, on the contrary, to identify the causes of the problems hindering it, to search for more effective ways of working based on the technological approach;

3. To learn the unique methods of teaching advanced pedagogical technologies of experienced teachers, identifying their differences and similarities, shortcomings and achievements, and applying them in their work.

One of the skills that every teacher should acquire at the present time is the ability to organize and conduct lessons based on pedagogical technologies. According to its composition, this skill is also interesting and complex. We came to the following conclusions as a result of interviews with our observers, experienced pedagogues, and study of educational methodological and scientific sources related to the topic.

- in order to organize lessons based on pedagogical technology, first of all, it is necessary to make effective use of the process of training sessions, to prepare thoroughly for the lesson from the theoretical and practical side;
- to be able to consciously and effectively apply the theoretical, pedagogical-psychological and methodical knowledge acquired by the teacher during training sessions and to be further strengthened;
- implementation of pedagogical technologies and achieving systematic implementation based on a specific goal, project;

So, pedagogical technology is a method of education, in a certain sense, a set of educational processes, tools, forms and methods. Selection of educational materials, reworking, changing the form and size of the subject according to the specific structure of the subject, the ability of the students, the level of mastery of the subject is also related to the educational technology. The fact that the teacher organizes the educational process on the basis of technological methods largely depends on him, his knowledge and familiarity with the organizational structure of each of them is an important guarantee of ensuring the effectiveness of education. The teacher should be well aware of the knowledge related to the meaningful and effective organization of pedagogical technologies in the application of them, be able to evaluate the positive effects of the used technologies on the effectiveness of the lesson and analyze the results, be able to draw appropriate conclusions, and have a critical attitude to their own activities. It is important to be able to connect students' active participation in the lesson by connecting their own knowledge with practical activities. Therefore, it is necessary for all science teachers, including music teachers, to be well aware of advanced interactive technologies. Because the content, goals and tasks of education are expanding as a result of the development of science. In this process, the forms and methods of teaching are improving. As a result, the main directions of human activity, i.e., education and training in the educational system, are turning into an integrated system, i.e., technologies, which provide opportunities for the full implementation of the intended goals.

So, pedagogical technology consists of the activity of influencing a person according to a predetermined goal. It is also a process that guarantees to teach the student to think independently, observe, acquire knowledge, and become an active participant in the lesson.

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